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FACULTY OF ENGINEERING
MECHANICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT
THERMAL SECTION**

Project on

**NONDESTRUCTIVE TESTING METHODS IN
AL-HESWA POWER PLANT AND
SANA'A INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT**

SUPERVISOR: DR. MAEN GARADA

Prepared by:

SAMER SAMEER A.RAHMAN HAYEL	081001
MOHAMMED RIYADH FUDHAIL	081093
YOUSEF KHALED ABDO	081013
SABR RASHAD MOHAMMED ALI	086026

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CARTIFICATE

Certified that the project work entitled:

Nondestructive Testing Methods in Al-Heswa Power Plant and Sana'a International Airport.

Submitted by:

SAMER SAMEER A.RAHMAN HAYEL	081001
MOHAMMED RIYADH FUDHAIL	081093
YOUSEF KHALED ABDO	081013
SABR RASHAD MOHAMMED ALI	086026

For award of B.Sc.Degree in Mechanical Engineering is an authentic record of bonafide work carried out by them under my supervision and guidance.

Supervisor: Dr. Maen Garada

Signature:

Date:

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Name:

Signatures:

SAMER SAMEER A.RAHMAN HAYEL

MOHAMMED RIYADH FUDHAIL

YOUSEF KHALED ABDO

SABR RASHAD MOHAMMED ALI

ABSTRACT

This project " Nondestructive Testing methods in Al-Heswa Power Plant and Sana'a International Airport ", consist of three chapters and a conclusion.

Chapter one is an introduction in which the main aim of this project is given, chapter two is a theoretical description of the NDT methods that used there, and chapter three is the practical application of these methods in Al-Heswa Power Plant and Sana'a International Airport. In the conclusion, we mention the difficulties that faced the project and piece of advice.

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LIST OF NOMENCLATURES

Symbol	Description	Unit
V	Velocity	m/s
V _L	Longitudinal wave velocity	m/s
V _S	Shear wave velocity	m/s
Λ	Wavelength	M
F	Frequency	Hz
E	Modulus of elasticity	N/mm ²
P	Density	g/cm ³
μ	Poisson's ratio	–
G	Shear modulus	N/mm ²
Θ _i	Angle of incident	Degree(°)
Θ _r	Angle of reflected wave	Degree (°)
V ₁	Velocity of incident wave	m/s
V ₂	Velocity of reflected wave	m/s
Z	Acoustic impedance	Kg/m ² /s
Z ₁	Acoustic impedance of medium 1	Kg/m ² /s
Z ₂	Acoustic Impedance of Medium 2	Kg/m ² /s
R	Reflection coefficient	–
T	Transmission coefficients	–
Δ	Standard depth of penetration	mm
ρ [*]	Resistivity	Ω·m
μ _r	Relative permeability	m ²
ND	Notch depth	mm

Chapter 1

Introduction

In this chapter a full overview of the project and the orientation of it will be illustrated.

1.1. Aim Of The Project:

The project aimed to answer the following questions:-

- What is material testing means and what is the different between destructive and nondestructive testing?
- What are the most important methods of nondestructive tests ?
- What are the principles that the nondestructive testing based on?
- How we can decide which method of NDT we can use ? And according to what we make our decision ?
- What are the procedures of the testing ?
- What are the defects that can be found in the materials and objects?

1.2. Significant Of The Project:

In the beginning of the 20th century , a renewed interest in the physics of the solid state and advancement in knowledge of the microstructure of materials , particularly metals , are bringing about a more basic understanding of the behavior of the materials. This interest guided the scientists to improve the methods of testing and inspection of the materials . And the industrial and technical world is becoming increasingly test-minded .Generally, engineers, architects, builders, industrial designers and managers are familiar with the idea of testing and are coming to rely more and more on tests as a basis for making many important decisions.

The science of the nondestructive testing is the science of the future , it uses to locate flaws and characterize material conditions otherwise cause planes to crash, reactors to fail, trains to derail, pipelines to burst, and a variety of less visible, but equally troubling events.

Despite the important of the nondestructive testing, there are not projects discussed it in details in our faculty.

This project tries to give the subject of the nondestructive testing more importance and discusses it in more details. It may be a good reference for the students whose interested in the nondestructive testing and helpful for those who want to work in this field.

1.3. Limitation Of The Project:

The project was done in two different locations in Yemen, Al-Heswa power station in Aden and the Sana'a international airport in Sana'a:

1.3.1. Al-Heswa power station:

Al-Heswa thermal power station and desalination complex– Aden which founded in 1982. It is a thermoelectric plant located on the coast of Aden and the oldest one in Republic of Yemen.

Al-Heswa station recently produce 180MW from electrical power. It has six turbines and boilers. Sixth turbine is Chinese. Most of machines there are Russian. It has section of safety, central workshop, material inspection department , training center, pumps vertical and horizontal (vertical pumps are used to draw the sea water), filters, and fire-brigade...etc. It has tanks for fuel as mazot , diesel, and oil. The fuel is supplied from Aden Refinery Company.

In Al-Heswa power station , our work was the inspection to detect defects in tubes. In this station the most commonly used test methods are the liquid penetrant method which is here a portable type (cleaner , penetrant , developer), and ultrasonic testing method to measure the pipe thickness only . They have also the magnetic particle inspection (MPI) for detection of defects , we understand how it works but we did not have the chance to used it there at a work location. The ultrasonic testing (UT) is also not used there for detection of defects but for measuring the thickness of the tubes.

1.3.2. Sana'a international airport:

The major part of this project was done in Al- Yemenia Maintenance and Engineering Division [MED], in Sana'a International Airport.

Yemenia Maintenance and Engineering Division (MED) facility consist two hangers (hanger A and B) dedicated to aircraft maintenance which accommodate as well hanger crew office and rest room, third party office production planning and control (PPC) booth, inspection office and hanger crew lavatory.

The component of maintenance facilities battery shop, paint workshop, upholstery workshop, technical training school, mechanical and electrical calibration workshop, electrical and electronics (Avionics) workshop, non-destructive testing (NDT) work shop.

The project was done in the NDT workshop which consist of three sections^[1]:

- Section A : which contains instruments required for eddy current inspection , ultrasonic inspection and borescope inspection .
- Section B : Accommodate all parts required for dye penetrant inspection and the magnetic particles inspection , and contains chemical solutions for dye penetrant and magnetic particles inspection.
- Section C : X-ray film processing room .

We trained only in sections A and B.

In Sana'a international airport the non-destructive testing (NDT) was often used for testing the wheels of the airplanes because their wheels are the parts subjected to stresses , these stresses may cause fracture of the wheels which leads to catastrophic failure of airplanes and people may loss their

life . In the Yemenia Maintenance and Engineering Division the inspectors are highly qualified people and they use only five non-destructive testing methods in their work.

More details about the non-destructive testing methods will be discussed later.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Part

2.1. Definitions^[2]:

At the beginning, there are important terms must be known, because they will be used and repeated in the project. The most important terms are:

2.1.1 Testing:

The most appropriate definition of the word “test(ing)” in the science of metallurgy is “to determine the presence or properties of a substance” and, to exhibit a given characteristic when subjected to a test.

2.1.2 Destructive Testing (DT):

Is a form of mechanical test (primarily destructive) of materials whereby certain specific characteristics of the material can be evaluated quantitatively. In some cases, the test specimens being tested are subjected to controlled conditions that simulate service. The information that is obtained through destructive testing is quite precise, but it only applies to the specimen being examined. Since the specimen is destroyed or mechanically changed, it is unlikely that it can be used for other purposes beyond the mechanical test.

2.1.3 Nondestructive Testing (NDT):

A general definition of nondestructive testing (NDT) is an examination, test, or evaluation performed on any type of test object without changing or altering that object in any way, The simplest of all definitions is basically an examination that is performed on an object of any type, size, shape or material to determine the presence or absence of discontinuities, or to evaluate other material characteristics.

2.2. Comparison Of Destructive And Nondestructive Testing:

The table below shows the differences between Destructive Testing (DT) and Nondestructive Testing (NDT).

Table (2.1)^[3]: Destructive Testing versus Nondestructive Testing

DESTRUCTIVE TESTS	NONDESTRUCTIVE TESTS
Test usually simulate one or more service conditions. Consequently , they tend to measure serviceability directly and reliably.	Tests usually involve indirect measurements of properties of no direct significance in service. The correlation between these measurements and serviceability must be proved by other means.
Tests are usually quantitative measurements of load for failure, significant distortion or damage, or life to failure under given loading and environmental conditions. Consequently they	Tests are usually qualitative and rarely quantitative. They do not usually measure load for failure or life to failure , even indirectly. They may, however, reveal damage or expose the mechanisms of failure.

may yield numerical data useful for design purposes or for establishing standards or specifications.	
The correlation between most destructive test measurements and the material properties being measured (particularly under simulated service loading) is usually direct. Hence most observers may agree upon the results of the test and their significance with respect to the serviceability of the material or part.	Skilled judgment and test or service experience are usually required to interpret test indications. Where the essential correlation has not been proven, or where experience is limited, observers may disagree in evaluating the significance of test indications.
Tests are not made on the objects actually used in service. Consequently the correlation or similarity between the objects tests and those used in serviceability of the material or part.	Tests are made directly upon the objects to be used in service. Consequently there is no doubt that the tests were made on representative test objects.
Tests can be made on only a fraction of the production lot to be used in service. They may have little value when the properties vary unpredictably from unit to unit.	Tests can be made on every unit to be used in service, if economically justified. Consequently they may be used even when great differences from unit occur in production lots.
Tests often cannot be made on complete production parts. The tests are often limited to test bars cut from production parts or from special material specimens processed to simulate the properties of the parts to be used in service.	Tests may be made on the entire production part or in all critical regions of it. Consequently the evaluation applies to the part as a whole. Many critical sections of the part may be examined simultaneously or sequentially as convenient and expedient.
A single destructive test may measure only one or a few of the properties that may be critical under service condition.	Many nondestructive tests, each sensitive to different properties or regions of the material or part, may be applied simultaneously or in sequence. In this way it is feasible to measure as many different properties correlated with service performance as desired.
Destructive tests are not usually convenient to apply to parts in service. Generally, service must be interrupted and the part permanently removed from service.	Nondestructive tests may often be applied to parts in service assemblies without interruption of service beyond normal maintenance or idle periods. They involve no loss of serviceable parts.
Cumulative change over a period of time cannot	Nondestructive tests permit repeated checks of a given

<p>readily be measured on a single unit. If several units from the same lot or service are tested in succession over a period of time, it must be proven that the units were initially similar. If the units are used in service and removed after various periods of time, it must be proven that each was subject to similar condition of service, before valid data can be obtained.</p>	<p>unit over a period of time. In this way, the rate of service damage, if detectable, and its correlation with service failure may be established clearly.</p>
<p>With parts of very high material or fabrication costs, the cost of replacing the parts destroyed may be prohibitive. It may not be feasible to make an adequate number and variety of destructive tests.</p>	<p>Acceptable parts of very high material or fabrication costs are not lost in nondestructive testing. Repeated testing during production or service is feasible when economically and practically justified.</p>
<p>Many destructive tests require extensive machining or other preparation of the test specimens. Often, massive precision-testing machines are required. In consequence the cost of destructive testing may be very high, and the number of samples that can be prepared and tested may make severe demands upon the time of highly skilled workers.</p>	<p>Little or no specimen preparation is required for many forms of nondestructive tests. Several forms of nondestructive testing equipment are portable. Many are capable of rapid testing or sorting and in some cases may be made fully automatic. The cost of nondestructive tests is less, in most cases, both per object tested and for overall testing, than the cost of adequate destructive tests.</p>
<p>The time and man-hour requirement of many destructive tests are very high. Excessive production costs may be incurred if adequate and expensive destructive tests are used as the primary method of production quality control.</p>	<p>Most non-destructive tests methods are rapid and require far fewer man-hours or actual hours than do typical destructive tests. Consequently testing all the production units cost normally less than, or comparable, to the costs of inspecting destructively only a minor percentage of the units in production lots.</p>

2.3. The Principles Of The Nondestructive Testing Methods:

2.3.1. Principles of liquid penetrant testing:

Liquid penetrant testing can be defined as a physical and chemical nondestructive testing procedure designed to detect and expose surface connected discontinuities in nonporous engineering materials^[4]. The method relies on the physical interaction between an appropriately formulated chemical liquid and the surface of a part. This interaction causes the liquid to enter surface cavities and later to emerge, visually indicating the location and approximate size and shape of the surface opening.

A very early surface inspection technique involved the rubbing of carbon black on glazed pottery, whereby the carbon black would settle in surface cracks rendering them visible. Later, at the 19th century to approximately 1940 used to examine iron and steel components by the "oil and whiting (chalk)" method. After that the method developed by using lacquer instead of chalk^[5].

1. Physics of the method:

A- Principles involved in liquid penetrant testing^[5]:

Liquid penetrant inspection depends mainly on a penetrant's effectively wetting the surface of a solid workpiece or specimen, flowing over that surface to form a continuous and reasonably uniform coating, and then migrating into cavities that are open to the surface. The cavities of interest are usually exceedingly small, often invisible to the unaided eye. The ability of a given liquid to flow over a surface and enter surface cavities depends principally on the following:

- Cleanliness of the surface
- Configuration of the cavity
- Cleanliness of the cavity
- Size of surface opening of the cavity
- Surface tension of the liquid
- Ability of the liquid to wet the surface
- Contact angle of the liquid^[6]

So there is three Principles exactly used in this method:

1- Surface tension of liquid:

Surface tension is a cohesive force exerted by the surface molecules of a liquid, making the surface below like a elastic membrane, Surface tension of liquid shown in the figure below:

Fig.2.1. Surface tension of liquid

2- Capillary action:

Every step of the penetrant process is done to promote capillary action. This is the phenomenon of a liquid rising or climbing when confined to small openings due to surface wetting properties of the liquid. The capillary action shown in the figure below:

Fig.2.2. Capillary action

3- Wetability:

The cohesive forces between molecules of a liquid cause surface tension. The cohesive force responsible for surface tension competes with the adhesive force between the molecules of the liquid and the solid surface. These forces jointly determine the contact angle, θ , between the liquid and the surface (Fig.2.3). If θ is less than 90° (Fig.2.4. a), the liquid is said to wet the surface, or to have good wetting ability; if the angle is equal to or greater than 90° (Fig.2.4. b and c), the wetting ability is considered poor.

Fig.2.3. Wetting characteristics as evaluated by the contact angle, θ , between a droplet of liquid and a solid surface

Fig.2.4. Types of wetability

B- Natural work of liquid penetrant testing^[5]:

In penetrant testing, a liquid with high surface wetting characteristics is applied to the surface of a component under test. The penetrant “penetrates” into surface breaking discontinuities via capillary action and other mechanisms. Excess penetrant is removed from the surface and a developer is applied to pull trapped penetrant back the surface. With good inspection technique, visual indications of any discontinuities present become apparent, the figure 2.4, shows the Natural work of liquid penetrant testing.

Fig. 2.5. Natural work of liquid penetrant testing

2. Materials and equipments of the method^[6]:

A- Materials of the method:

There are some materials which used in Liquid Penetrant Testing, as:

1- Penetrant:

It is a chemical materials applied to the inspected surface to test it and finding the discontinuity in a work-piece. The penetrant changes in its Sensitivity levels.

i- Sensitivity Levels:

Penetrants are also formulated to produce a variety of sensitivity levels. The higher the sensitivity level, the smaller the defect that the penetrant system is capable of detecting.

The five sensitivity levels are:

- Level 4 - Ultra-High Sensitivity
- High Sensitivity
- Medium Sensitivity
- Low Sensitivity
- Ultra Low Sensitivity

Note:

Sensitivity Levels are applied to Type I penetrant system (Fluorescent liquid Penetran) only, but Type II penetrant system (Visible liquid Penetran) is level 1 .

2- Developers:

Developer is a material used to pull the trapped penetrant material out of defects and spread it out on the surface of the part so it can be seen by an inspector.

The fine developer particles both reflect and refract the incident ultraviolet light, allowing more of it to interact with the penetrant, causing more efficient fluorescence. The developer also allows more light to be emitted through the same mechanism. This is why indications are brighter than the penetrant itself under UV light. Another function that some developers perform is to create a white background so there is a greater degree of contrast between the indication and the surrounding background.

i- Developer forms:

The Developers classify into six standard forms. These forms are listed below:

- Form a - Dry Powder
- Form b - Water Soluble
- Form c - Water Suspendable
- Form d - Nonaqueous Type 1 Fluorescent (Solvent Based)
- Form e - Nonaqueous Type 2 Visible Dye (Solvent Based)
- Form f - Special Applications

The project have been applied by {Form d - Nonaqueous Type 1 Fluorescent (Solvent Based)} and {Form e - Nonaqueous Type 2 Visible Dye (Solvent Based)} so the project will talk upon them:

Note:

The two forms of Developers no. {Form d - Nonaqueous Type 1 Fluorescent (Solvent Based)} ,and no{5. Form e - Nonaqueous Type 2 Visible Dye (Solvent Based)}are relatively same, so just Nonaqueous form will be explained.

Nonaqueous: Nonaqueous developers suspend the developer in a volatile solvent and are typically applied with a spray gun. Nonaqueous developers are commonly distributed in aerosol spray cans for portability. The solvent tends to pull penetrant from the indications by solvent action, the figure below shows Nonaqueous developer.

Fig.2.6. Nonaqueous developer

3- Emulsifiers:

Emulsifiers are liquids used to render excess penetrant on the surface of a workpiece water washable. There are two methods used in the postemulsifiable method: method B, lipophilic, and method D, hydrophilic.

Note:

The two methods used in the post-emulsifiable method: method B, lipophilic, and method D, hydrophilic will mention in the classification of this method.

4- Pre- and post-test cleaning materials:

The list below shows the pre- and post- test cleaning materials :

- Developers
- Emulsifiers
- Pre- and post-test cleaning materials
- Proper cleaning
- Immersion tanks and detergent solutions
- Vapor degreasing
- Steam cleaning
- Solvent cleaning
- Rust and surface scale
- Paint removal

- Etching
- Surface cleaning processes to be avoided

B- Equipments of the method^[6]:

The Penetrant Test Equipment divided into three types :

- Stationary
- Portable
- Automated

The project will take about Stationary and Portable only.

1- Stationary:

Stationary equipment used in liquid penetrant testing varies in size and is largely dependent upon the size of the test specimen. Depending on the type and process used, a stationary system could include the following as in the fig. (2.7.):

- Penetrant station (tank)
- Drain station
- Emulsification station (tank)
- Rinse station (tank)
- Developing station (tank)
- Drying station (usually oven)
- Inspection station (enclosed booth or table with proper lighting)
- Post-cleaning station (usually in remote area)

Fig.2.7. Stationary system

2- Portable:

Both visible and fluorescent dye penetrants are available in kits which can be used at a remote location or when testing a small portion of a large article.

A visible dye penetrant kit usually contains:

- Pressurized spray cans of cleaning or removal fluid
- Pressurized spray cans of visible dye penetrant
- Pressurized spray cans of non-aqueous developer
- Wiping cloths and brushes

A fluorescent dye penetrant kit usually contains:

- A portable black light and transformer
- Pressurized spray cans of cleaning or removal fluid
- Pressurized spray cans of fluorescent dye penetrant
- Pressurized spray cans of non-aqueous developer
- Wiping cloths and brushes

The following figures show the cans of cleaner , penetrant , developer , cloths and brushes , portable black light, respectively:

cleaner , penetrant , developer

cloths and brushes

portable black light

Fig.2.8. Portable equipments

3. Application of the method^[5]:

- The method cannot be used for the materials which are with rough surfaces, or porous ceramics, wood and other fibrous materials, plastic parts that absorb or react with the penetrant materials and components with coatings that prevent penetrants from entering defects.
- The method used to detect the defects that are open to the surface, such as :
Rolled products: cracks, seams, laminations

Castings: cold shuts, hot tears, porosity, blow holes, shrinkage

Forgings: cracks, laps, external bursts

Welds: cracks, porosity, undercut, overlap, lack of fusion, lack of penetration

The figure 2.9. below shows the types of discontinuities which can be detected by liquid penetrant testing:

Fig.2.9. The discontinuities which can be detected by liquid penetrant testing

4. Classifications of the method^[4]:

There are two types of classification of the liquid penetrant testing, the figure below illustrate that two types of classification:

Fig.2.10. Classification of Liquid Penetrants

A- Classification of liquid penetrants by dye type:

Liquid penetrants are generally classified according to the dye contained in the liquid penetrant into three types :

- Fluorescent penetrant
- Visible dye penetrants
- Dual sensitivity penetrants

The project have been applied on the Fluorescent and Visible dye penetrants, so the project will talk about them only:

1- Fluorescent penetrant:

Fluorescent liquid penetrants contain fluorescent dye that emits yellowish green light when exposed to near ultraviolet radiation (with a wavelength of 320 to 400 nm). This property is termed fluorescence.

2- Visible dye penetrants:

Visible dye or color contrast liquid penetrants contain a colored (usually red) dye that is visible under natural or white light. The visibility is further enhanced during the liquid penetrant process by the application of a white developer. Red dye is most common.

The table below compares between visible liquid penetrant and fluorescent liquid penetrant:

Table (2.2): Comparison visible liquid penetrant and fluorescent liquid penetrant

Types of penetrant \ Types of compare	Visible liquid Penetrant	Fluorescent liquid Penetrant
1. Inspection performed material	Visible penetrant materials	fluorescent penetrant materials
2. Color of penetrant	Red (mostly)	Green (mostly)
3. Light used to inspect	white light normal area	ultraviolet light in a darkened area
3. Sensitivity	Less Sensitivity	More Sensitivity
4. Sensitivity level	Level 1 Sensitivity range	From 1 to 4 Sensitivity range
5. Illustrated figure (2.11) and (2.12) respectively		

B- Classification of Liquid Penetrants by Removal Method:

A liquid penetrant is further classified by the technique used to remove it from the surface of a part after it has been on the part a specified amount of dwell time during the test process into four types:

- Water washable, method A
- Postemulsifiable lipophilic, method B

- Solvent removable, method C
- Postemulsifiable hydrophilic, method D

The project have been applied on the water washable, method A and Solvent removable, method C, so the project will talk about them only:

1- Water washable, method A^[6]:

It designed so that the penetrant is directly water washable from the surface of the workpiece; It can be used to process workpieces quickly and efficiently. It is important, however, that the washing operation be carefully controlled because water-washable penetrants are susceptible to overwashing. The essential operations involved in this method are illustrated schematically in Fig.2.13, and flow diagram Fig.2.14.

Fig.2.13. Five essential operations for liquid penetrant inspection using the water-washable system

Fig.2.14, Processing flow diagram for the water-washable liquid penetrant system

2- Solvent removable, method C^[6]:

It is available for use when it is necessary to inspect only a localized area of a workpiece or to inspect a workpiece at the site rather than on a production inspection basis. Normally, the same type of solvent is used for pre-cleaning and for removing excess penetrant. This penetrant process is convenient and broadens the range of applications of penetrant inspections. However, because the solvent-removable method is labor intensive, it is not practical for many production applications. When properly conducted and when used in the appropriate applications, the solvent-removable method can be one of the most sensitive penetrant methods available. The operations for this process are illustrated schematically in Fig. 2.15, and Fig. 2.16, Processing flow diagram

Fig. 2.15. Operations (in addition to pre-cleaning) for the solvent-removable liquid penetrant system

Fig. 2.16. Processing flow diagram for the solvent-removable liquid penetrant system

The table below shows the different between the two methods:

Table (2.3): Advantages and disadvantages of water washable and solvent-removable method

Types of Removals	<u>Advantages</u>	<u>Disadvantages</u>
<u>Water-Washable</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easily washed with water - Good for quantities of small specimens - Good on rough surfaces - Good on keyways and threads - Good on wide range of discontinuities - Fast, single step process - Relatively inexpensive - Available in oxygen compatible form 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not reliable for detecting scratches and similar shallow surface discontinuities - Not reliable on reruns of specimen - Not reliable on anodized surfaces - Acids and chromates affect sensitivity -Easily over-washed - Penetrant subject to water contamination
<u>Solvent-Removable</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Portability - No water required - Good on anodized specimens - Good for spot checking - Specimens can be rerun 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flammable materials - Removal of excess surface penetrant is time consuming - Materials cannot be used in open tanks - Difficult to use on rough surfaces such as cast magnesium

2.3.2. Principles of magnetic particles testing:

Magnetic particles testing is a method of locating surface and subsurface discontinuities in ferromagnetic materials.

The earliest known use of magnetism to inspect an object took place as early as 1868. Cannon barrels were checked for defects by magnetizing the barrel then sliding a magnetic compass along the barrel's length. These early inspectors were able to locate flaws in the barrels by monitoring the needle of the compass. This was a form of nondestructive testing but the term was not commonly used until sometime after World War I ^[7].

It is a very useful and versatile NDT method. Some of the advantages of this method^[6]:

- The magnetic particle method is a sensitive means of locating small and shallow surface cracks in ferromagnetic materials.
- Discontinuities that do not actually break through the surface are also indicated in many cases by this method.
- Magnetic particle indications are produced directly on the surface of the part to be inspected.
- Staff can be trained rapidly to use the method.
- It is economical and can be done quickly.

1. Physics of the method:

A- Magnetizing current^[6]:

The fields produced by direct and alternating current differ in many respects. The important difference with regard to magnetic particle inspection is that the fields produced by direct current generally penetrate the cross section of the part, while the fields produced by alternating current are confined to the metal at or near the surface of the part, a phenomenon known as the skin effect. Therefore, alternating current should not be used in searching for subsurface discontinuities.

1- Direct current:

The best source of direct current is the rectification of alternating current to half wave direct current (HWDC) or to full wave direct current(FWDC):

Table (2.4): Types of direct current

Full-wave rectified:

3-phase:

Single phase:

- The current has the deepest possible penetration and must be used for inspection for defects below the surface when using the wet magnetic particle method.

Half-wave rectified:

single-phase:

- Provides the highest sensitivity for discontinuities that are wholly below the surface, such as those in castings and weldments.
- The current is advantageous for the dry powder method because it creates a pulsating unidirectional field that gives increased mobility to the particles.

2- Alternating current:

- Must be single-phase when used directly for magnetizing purposes, and usually has a frequency of 50 or 60 Hz.
- Used only for the detection of defects open to the surface.
- One problem encountered when alternating current is used is that the resultant residual magnetism in the part may not be at a level as high as that of the magnetism generated by the peak current of the ac cycle. This is because the level of residual magnetism depends on where in the cycle the current was discontinued.

B- The hysteresis loop and magnetic properties^[6]:

A great deal of information can be learned about the magnetic properties of a material by studying its hysteresis loop.

Table (2.5)^[3]: Hysteresis loop formation

	<p>Starting at the origin (O) with the specimen in the unmagnetized condition and increasing the magnetizing force in small increments, the flux in the material increases quite rapidly at first, then more slowly until it reaches a point beyond which any increase in the magnetizing force does not increase the flux density. This is shown by the dashed (virgin) curve Oa. In this condition, the specimen is said to be magnetically saturated.</p>
	<p>When the magnetizing force is gradually reduced to zero, curve ab results. The amount of magnetism that the steel retains at point b is called residual magnetism, B_r.</p>
	<p>When the magnetizing current is reversed and gradually increased in value, the flux continues to diminish. The flux does not become zero until point c is reached, at which time the magnetizing force is represented by O_c, which graphically designates the coercive force, H_c, in the material.</p> <p>Coercive force H_c:</p> <p>Is an additional force in the opposite direction of the magnetizing force causes the domains to return to their original random orientation.</p>

As the reversed field is increased beyond *c*, point *d* is reached (Fig. *d*). At this point, the specimen is again magnetically saturated. The magnetizing force is now decreased to zero, and the *de* line is formed and retains reversed-polarity residual magnetism, B_r , in the specimen.

Further increasing the magnetizing force in the original direction completes the curve *efa*. The cycle is now complete, and the area within the loop *abcdefa* is called the hysteresis curve.

The definite lag throughout the cycle between the magnetization force and the flux is called hysteresis.

From the hysteresis loop, a number of primary magnetic properties of a material can be determined^[7]:

- i- *Retentivity* - It is a material's ability to retain a certain amount of residual magnetic field when the magnetizing force is removed after achieving saturation. (The value of B at point *b* on the hysteresis curve.)
- ii- *Residual Magnetism or Residual Flux* - the magnetic flux density that remains in a material when the magnetizing force is zero. Note that residual magnetism and retentivity are the same when the material has been magnetized to the saturation point. However, the level of residual magnetism may be lower than the retentivity value when the magnetizing force did not reach the saturation level.
- iii- *Coercive Force* - The amount of reverse magnetic field which must be applied to a magnetic material to make the magnetic flux return to zero. (The value of H at point *c* on the hysteresis curve.)
- iv- *Permeability, μ* - A property of a material that describes the ease with which a magnetic flux is established in the component. ($\mu = B/H$)
- v- *Reluctance* - Is the opposition that a ferromagnetic material shows to the establishment of a magnetic field. Reluctance is analogous to the resistance in an electrical circuit.

C- The direction of the magnetic field^[6]:

1- Circular magnetization:

Electric current passing through any straight conductor such as a wire or bar creates a circular magnetic field around the conductor.

Under normal circumstances, a discontinuity such as A in the figure below would give no indication of its presence, because it is regular in shape and lies parallel to the magnetic field. If the discontinuity has an irregular shape but is predominantly parallel to the magnetic field, such as B, there is a good possibility that a weak indication would form. Where the predominant direction of the discontinuity is at a 45° angle to the magnetic field, such as C, D, and E, the conditions are more favorable for detection regardless of the shape of the discontinuity. Discontinuities whose predominant directions, regardless of shape, are at a 90° angle to the magnetic field produce the most pronounced indications (F, G, and H).

Fig.2.17. Indications in circular magnetizing

2- Longitudinal magnetization:

Electric current can also be used to create a longitudinal magnetic field in magnetic materials. When electric current is passed through a coil of one or more turns, a magnetic field is established lengthwise or longitudinally.

A longitudinally magnetized bar is shown in the figure below. Discontinuities L, M, and N, which are at about 45° to the magnetic field, would produce detectable indications as they would with a circular field. Discontinuities J and K would display pronounced indications, and weak indications would be produced at discontinuities P, Q, and R.

Fig.2.18. Indications in longitudinal magnetizing

D- Magnetic fields distribution and intensity in the conductor^[7]:

In the images below, the magnetic field strength is graphed versus distance from the center of the conductor:

It can be seen that in a nonmagnetic conductor carrying DC, the internal field strength rises from zero at the center to a maximum value at the surface of the conductor. The external field strength decrease with distance from the surface of the conductor. When the conductor is a magnetic material, the field strength within the conductor is much greater than it is in the nonmagnetic conductor. This is due to the permeability of the magnetic material. The external field is exactly the same for the two materials provided the current level and conductor radius are the same.

When the conductor is carrying alternating current, the internal magnetic field strength rises from zero at the center to a maximum at the surface. However, the field is concentrated in a thin layer near the surface of the conductor. This is known as the "skin effect". The external field decreases with increasing distance from the surface as it does with DC. It should be remembered that with AC the field is constantly varying in strength and direction.

In a hollow circular conductor there is no magnetic field in the void area. The magnetic field is zero at the inside wall surface and rises until it reaches a maximum at the outside wall surface. As

with a solid conductor. The external field strength decreases with distance from the surface of the conductor. The external field is exactly the same for the two materials provided the current level and conductor radius are the same.

When AC is passed through a hollow circular conductor, the skin effect concentrates the magnetic field at the outside diameter of the component.

The direct method of magnetization is not recommended when inspecting the inside diameter wall of a hollow component for shallow defects. The field strength increases rapidly as one moves out (into the material) from the ID, so if the defect has significant depth, it may be detectable.

However, a much better method of magnetizing hollow components for inspection of the ID and OD surfaces is with the use of a central conductor. As can be seen in the field distribution image below, when current is passed through a nonmagnetic central conductor (copper bar), the magnetic field produced on the inside diameter surface of a magnetic tube is much greater and the field is still strong enough for defect detection on the OD surface.

The magnetic field distribution in and around a nonmagnetic central conductor carrying DC inside a hollow conductor of a magnetic material .

E- Methods of generating magnetic fields:

General applications, advantages, and limitations of the various methods of magnetizing parts for magnetic particle inspection are summarized in the table below:

Table (2.6)^[6]: Generating magnetic field methods

Description	Advantages	Limitations
1- Coil Method:		
Flow current in a coil placed around the test article.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All generally longitudinal surfaces are longitudinally magnetized to locate transverse discontinuities. - Longitudinal field easily attained by wrapping with a flexible cable. - Easy and fast, especially where residual method is applicable. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Part should be centered in coil to maximize length effectively magnetized during a given shot. - Multiple processing may be required because of part shape. - Sensitivity diminishes at ends of part because of general leakage field pattern.
2- Central Conductors or through conductor method:		
Flow current through a conductor laid in a hole in the part to be examine .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No electrical contact, so that possibility of burning is eliminated. - Circumferentially directed magnetic field is generated in all surfaces surrounding the conductor. - Ideal for parts for which the residual method is applicable. - Lightweight parts can be supported by 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Size of conductor must be ample to carry required current. - Ideally, conductor should be centrally located within hole. - Large-diameter parts require several setups with conductor near or against inner surface and rotation of part between setups.

	<p>the central conductor.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multiple turns can be used to reduce the amount of current required. - Both inside (ID) and outside (OD) surfaces can be inspected. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where continuous method is being employed, inspection is required after each setup. - Sensitivity of outer surface to indications may be somewhat diminished relative to inner surface for large-diameter and thick-wall parts.
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3- Yoke Method:

<p>Placed the test article or the part under test between the opposite poles of an electromagnet or permanent magnet.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No electrical contact. Highly portable. - Can locate discontinuities in any direction, with proper yoke orientation. - Good sensitivity to surface discontinuities. - Highly portable. - Wet or dry method can be used. - Alternating current yoke can also serve as demagnetizer in some cases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time consuming. - Yoke must be systematically repositioned to locate discontinuities with random orientation. - Relatively good contact must be established between part and poles of yoke. - Complex part shape may cause difficulty. - Poor sensitivity to subsurface discontinuities except in isolated areas.
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4- Direct Contact, Head Shot Method:

<p>Like the process of the horizontal method unit , the current passes through the tested article by the heads of the bench unit. It can be axial or cross current.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fast and easy process. - Complete circular field surrounds entire current path. - Good sensitivity to surface and near-surface discontinuities. - Simple as well as relatively complex parts can usually be easily inspected with one or more shots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility of burning part exists if proper contact conditions are not met. - Long parts should be inspected in sections to facilitate bath application without resorting to an excessively long current shot.
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5- Direct Contact, Clamps And Cables Method:		
<p>Flow current directly along the longitudinal axis of the test article or across it by a clamps and cables.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Large surface areas can be inspected in a relatively short time. - Entire length can be circularly magnetized by contacting end-to-end. - Entire length can be circularly magnetized by contacting end-to-end. - Amperage requirements are independent of length. No loss of magnetism at ends 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High amperage requirements (8000-20,000 A) dictate use of special direct current power pack. - Effective field is limited to outer surface so process cannot be used to inspect inner surface. - Part ends must be shaped to permit electrical contact and must be able to carry required current without excessive heating.
6- Prod Contacts Method:		
<p>Conduct current to the test article by attaching two prods to the appropriate points on it.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circular field can be selectively directed to weld area by prod placement. - In conjunction with half-wave current and dry powder, provides excellent sensitivity to subsurface discontinuities. - Prods, cables, and power packs can be brought to inspection site. - Entire surface area can be inspected in small increments using nominal current values. - Circular magnetic field can be concentrated in specific areas likely to contain discontinuities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Only small area can be inspected at one time. - Arc burn can result from poor contact. - Surface must be dry when dry powder is being used. - Prod spacing must be in accordance with magnetizing current level. - Coverage of large surface areas requires a multiplicity of shot.

According to the application of magnetism to the test article ,we have two types of magnetizing in the magnetic particle inspection , residual and continuous.

Table (2.7): Residual Magnetism Vs Continuous Magnetism

Residual Magnetism	Continuous Magnetism
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The method can be used only on parts made of metals having sufficient retentivity. - It must be strong enough to produce leakage fields at discontinuities. - This method is reliable only for detecting surface discontinuities. - The dry or the wet method of applying particles can be used with this method. - With the wet method, the magnetized parts can either be immersed in a gently agitated bath of suspended or flooded by a curtain spray. The time of immersion of the part in the bath can affect the strength of the indications. - Particles buildup will be greatest on horizontal upper surfaces and will be less on vertical surfaces and horizontal lower surfaces. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The continuous method used on any metal that can be magnetized because in this method residual magnetism and retentivity are not as important in producing a leakage field at a discontinuity. - This method is mandatory for inspection of low-carbon steels or iron having little or no retentivity. - It is frequently used with alternating current on such metals because the AC field produces excellent mobility of dry magnetic particles. - Maximum sensitivity for the detection of very fine discontinuities is achieved by immersing the part in a wet-particle bath, passing the magnetizing current through the part for a short time during immersion, and leaving the current on as the part is removed and while the bath drains from the surface.

F- Demagnetization^[8]:

There are many demagnetization methods , the table below illustrate the important methods:

Table (2.8): Demagnetization Methods

Withdrawal from Alternating Current Coil	<p>The fastest and most simple technique is to pass the part through a high intensity alternating current coil and then slowly withdraw the part from the field of the coil.</p> <p>This should be repeated as necessary to reduce the residual field to an acceptable level.</p> <p>Use of this technique may not be effective on large parts in which the alternating magnetic current field is insufficient to penetrate.</p>
Decreasing Alternating Current	<p>An alternative technique for part demagnetization is subjecting the part to the alternating magnetic field while gradually reducing its strength to a desired level.</p>

Demagnetizing with Yokes	Alternating current yokes may be used for local demagnetization by placing the poles on the surface, moving them around the area, and slowly withdrawing the yoke while it is still energized.
Reversing Direct Current	The part to be demagnetized is subjected to consecutive steps of reversed and reduced direct current magnetization to a desired level. (This is the most effective process of demagnetizing large parts in which the alternating current field has insufficient penetration to remove the internal residual magnetization.) This technique requires special equipment for reversing the current while simultaneously reducing it in small increments.
Heating The Material	heat a material above its curie temperature[(Tc), or Curie point [the temperature where a material's permanent magnetism changes to induced magnetism] .

2. Equipments and materials^[6]:

A- *Medium:*

It refers to particles that have the ability to be strongly attracted to leakage fields. The particles may be in the form of dry powder or they may be suspended in liquid carrier. They can be fluorescent or visible.

The particles in both the wet and dry method must have the following properties:

- be non-toxic;
- be finely divided and within correct size range;
- be ferromagnetic;
- be free of contaminants;
- possess high permeability;
- possess low retentivity; and
- provide high color contrast (visibility)

Four factors enter into the selection of a satisfactory medium. These factors have a great effect on the quality of the indications obtained when performing a magnetic particle test:

- Magnetic Properties.
- Geometric properties.
- Mobility.
- Visibility.

B- Magnetizing Machine:

1- Bench Units:

For the production inspection of numerous parts that are relatively small but not necessarily identical in shape, a bench unit with contact heads for circular magnetization, as well as a built-in coil for longitudinal magnetization, is commonly used .

Fig.2.19. Wet horizontal magnetic particle test equipment

2- Mobile Equipment:

Often it is necessary to bring the test equipment to an article located in another area. Prods are usually used with mobile equipment.

3- Portable Units:

Table (2.9): Portable equipments

Type	Description
<p><u>1- The yoke:</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is the most useful type of the portable units - It used to produce a longitudinal field by using the part to complete a magnetic circuit. - It can be equipped to induce an AC or HWDC field in the component being inspected. - It is ideal for usage in a wet or potentially high explosive gas environment providing high inspection operator safety.
<p><u>2- Permanent magnet:</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It made of materials that have low permeability and high retentivity. - They are often used when high sensitivity is not required, electricity will create a safety hazard or electricity is not available. - They may be considered for use as a back-up method for verifying indications after an MT or PT test. - Magnets are made of hard carbon steel with fixed or articulated legs. - They should be stored with the legs folded together or a ferromagnetic keeper installed across the legs to avoid weakening of the magnet. - Repeated dropping of the magnet will also cause the magnet to lose strength.

C- Demagnetizing Equipment:

The most common type of stationary demagnetization equipment consists of a current carrying AC coil (2) and a mounting stand of some sort. Stationary equipment also includes a track (1) and carriage (3) to help the inspector move heavy or bulky parts through the coil. A rotary timer switch (4) is included to energize and de-energize the coil automatically. The timer in the power control switch will prevent the coil from accidentally being left on for long periods of time. This will cause the coil to overheat and catch fire. A red indicator light (5) will illuminate when power is on and the coil is energized.

Fig.2.20. Stationary demagnetizing unit

D- Magnetic Field Indicators:

There are a number of tools and methods available that are used to determine the presence and direction of the field surrounding a component:

Table (2.10): Field indicators

<p><u>2- Hall-Effect Meter or gauss meter:</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An electronic device that provides a readout of the magnetic field strength in gauss or tesla units. - The meters use a very small conductor or semiconductor element at the tip of the probe. - There are two kinds of gauss meter , simple type and digital type. - Used for measuring the peak value of a field.
<p><u>2- Ketos Ring:</u></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Is a disc made of tool steel. It measures 5" diameter x 7/8" thick with a 1-1/4" center hole. The disc has 12 holes, .070" diameter, drilled through the side of the disc at graduated depths below the circumferential surface. - A central conductor bar, a minimum of 1" diameter x 16" long, is passed through the center of the disc and the current is passing through it. - Gently apply particles to the surface of the ring while the current is flowing. - The number of hole indications visible should meet or exceed those as specified in the table below.

Table (2.11)^[9]: Ketos ring test values

Type of Suspension	Amperage FWDC	Minimum Number of Holes Indicated
Dry Powder	1400	4
	2500	6
	3400	7
Wet Non-Fluorescent (Red or Black)	1400	3
	2500	5
	3400	6
Wet Fluorescent	1400	3
	2500	5
	3400	6

E- Lights for Magnetic Particles Inspection^[7]:

In the magnetic particles inspection we have two types of lights that we need , white and black light .

1- Black light:

- Black light is defined as electromagnetic radiation in the near ultraviolet wavelength range.
- Required when performing fluorescent penetrant inspections or fluorescent magnetic particles inspection.
- The required wavelength of ultraviolet light is 365 nm or 3650 Å. It is at this wavelength that the fluorescent dye in the medium is activated.
- The minimum acceptable intensity is 1000 μW/cm² (10 W/m²) at 15 in. [38.1 cm] from the front of the filter to the face of the sensor at the surface being examined.
- Black lights shall be checked periodically for cleanliness and integrity and shall be cleaned, repaired or replaced as appropriate.

2- White light:

- Visible light shall be used when examining with non-fluorescent magnetic particles and for interpretation of indications found with fluorescent magnetic particles.
- A minimum light intensity of 100 fc (1000 lx) shall be available at the surface of the part undergoing examination or evaluation.

F- Miscellaneous Equipments:

1- Light meters:

- Meters used to measure the intensity of the lights used in the magnetic particle inspection.
- There are light meters specially for the white light and others for the black light.
- Light meters shall be calibrated at least once a year or whenever a meter has been repaired.

2- Centrifugal tube:

The centrifugal tube is used to check the suspension for particle concentration, contamination, brightness and dye separation. There are two types of the tubes , one for the fluorescent medium and the other for the non-fluorescent , they are different in the scale only.

Fig.2.21. Centrifugal tube

3. Application of the method^[21]:

The application of the magnetic particles inspection summarized in the table below:

Table (2.12): Applications of magnetic particles inspection method

Production processes	Types of Components	Industrial Sectors
<i>Primary Processing</i>		
- Forging bursts	- Ingots	- Petrochemical
- Forging laps	- Billets	- Construction
- Rolling laps, seams, and stringers	- Slabs	- Aircraft and aerospace
- Rolling seams	- Blooms	- Automotive
- Laminations (at the edges of plates and sheets)	- Bar stock	- Defense
- Casting shrinkage (at the surface)	- Sheet	- Nuclear
- Casting inclusions (at the surface)	- Rod	- Transportation
- Casting cold shuts (at the surface)	- Wire	- Shipping (marine)
- Casting hot tears (at the surface)	- Castings	
- Quench and heat cracks	- Shafts (plain, threaded, or splined)	
- Grinding cracks (or checks)	- Welds	
- Machining tears	- Bearings and bearing races	
- Plating cracks	- Nuts and bolts	
<i>Welding</i>	- Gears	
- Cracks (longitudinal, transverse, and crater)	- Cylinders	
- Lack of fusion	- Discs	
- Incomplete penetration (if accessible)	- Forgings	
- Entrapped slag	- Tubular products	
- Inclusions	- Plate	
- Overlap or “cold” lap		
<i>Service</i>		
- Fatigue cracks		
- Stress corrosion cracks		
- Static failure cracks (overstressed structures)		

2.3.3. Principle of ultrasonic testing:

Ultrasonic testing uses high frequency sound energy to conduct examinations and make measurements. The frequency of the mechanical waves used is much above the audible range of 20HZ to 20MHZ ^[10]. Ultrasonic testing can be conducted on a wide variety of material forms including castings, forgings, welds, and composites.

Prior to World War II, the technique of sending sound waves through water and observing the returning echoes to characterize submerged objects, inspired early ultrasound investigators to explore ways to apply the concept to medical diagnosis. In 1929 and 1935, Sokolov studied the use of ultrasonic waves in detecting metal objects.

Ultrasonic inspection is a very useful and versatile NDT method. Some of the advantages of ultrasonic inspection that are often cited include:

- It is sensitive to both surface and subsurface discontinuities.
- The depth of penetration for flaw detection or measurement is superior to other NDT methods.
- Only single-sided access is needed when the pulse-echo technique is used.
- It is highly accurate in determining reflector position and estimating size and shape.
- Minimal part preparation is required.
- Electronic equipment provides instantaneous results.
- Detailed images can be produced with automated systems.
- It has other uses, such as thickness measurement, in addition to flaw detection.

As with all NDT methods, ultrasonic inspection also has its limitations, which include:

- Surface must be accessible to transmit ultrasound.
- Skill and training is more extensive than with some other methods.
- It normally requires a coupling medium to promote the transfer of sound energy into the test specimen.
- Materials that are rough, irregular in shape, very small, exceptionally thin or not homogeneous are difficult to inspect.
- Cast iron and other coarse grained materials are difficult to inspect due to low sound transmission and high signal noise.
- Linear defects oriented parallel to the sound beam may go undetected.
- Reference standards are required for both equipment calibration and the characterization of flaws.

1. Physics of the method:

Sound is produced by a vibrating body and travels in the form of a wave. Sound waves travel through materials by vibrating the particles that make up the material. The pitch of the sound is determined by the frequency of the wave (vibrations or cycles completed in a certain period of time). Ultrasound is sound with a pitch too high to be detected by the human ear this is as shown in figure 2.22.

Fig.2.22. Basic principles of sound

The measurement of sound waves from crest to crest determines its wavelength (λ). The time it takes a sound wave to travel a distance of one complete wavelength is the same amount of time it takes the source to execute one complete vibration. The sound wavelength is inversely proportional to its frequency. ($\lambda = 1/f$) Several wave modes of vibration are used in ultrasonic inspection. The most common are longitudinal, shear, and Rayleigh (surface) waves as shown in figure 2.23^[11].

Fig.2.23.: Wavelength

Where:

T : Time period of vibration.

f : Frequency of vibration.($f = 1/T$ Cycles/sec (HZ))

A : Amplitude of vibration.

λ : Wavelength.

Ultrasonic waves are very similar to light waves in that they can be reflected refracted, and focused as shown in figure 2.24. Reflection and refraction occurs when sound waves interact with interfaces of differing acoustic properties. In solid materials, the vibration energy can be split into different wave modes when the wave encounters an interface at an angle other than 90 degrees. Ultrasonic reflections from the presence of discontinuities or geometric features enables detection and location. The velocity of sound in a given material is constant and can only be altered by a change in the mode of energy. The velocity of some material as shown in Table 1.13. The values of this table given from Appendix I ^[11].

Fig.2.24. Reflection and refraction of light

Table (2.13): Velocity of ultrasonic for some materials

MATERIAL	DENSITY (g/cm³)	LOGITUDINAL WAVES (V_L) (m/s)	SHEAR WAVES (V_S) (m/s)	Z* 10³Kg/m²/s
ALUMINUM	2.69	6300	3130	16947
STEEL	7.85	5940	3250	46629
PERSPEX	1.18	2730	1120	3221.4
WATER	1.0	1500	CAN NO TRAVEL IN LIQUIDS AND GASES	1500
OIL	0.95	11625		11043.74
AIR	0.0012	0.0033		0.430

NOTE:-

For a particular material the velocity of these waves is almost half of the longitudinal waves, example for that :

$$\text{For Steel } V_S / V_L = 0.55$$

A- Ultrasound generation:

Ultrasound is generated with a transducer. A piezoelectric element in the transducer converts electrical energy into mechanical vibrations (sound), and vice versa. The transducer is capable of both transmitting and receiving sound energy, this is as shown in figure 2.25^[12].

Fig.2.25. Ultrasound generation (transducer)

B- Principles of ultrasonic inspection^[1]:

Ultrasonic waves are introduced into a material where they travel in a straight line and at a constant speed until they encounter a surface. At surface interfaces some of the wave energy is reflected and some is transmitted. The amount of reflected or transmitted energy can be detected and provides information about the size of the reflector. The travel time of the sound can be measured and this provides information on the distance that the sound has traveled.

C- Test techniques:

Ultrasonic testing is a very versatile inspection method, and inspections can be accomplished in a number of different ways. Ultrasonic inspection techniques are commonly divided into three primary classifications^[10].

1- Pulse-echo & through transmission:

In pulse-echo testing, a transducer sends out a pulse of energy and the same or a second transducer listens for reflected energy (an echo). Reflections occur due to the presence of discontinuities and the surfaces of the test article. The amount of reflected sound energy is displayed versus time, which provides the inspector information about the size and the location of features that reflect the sound this is technique as shown in figures 2.26, 2.27^[7].

Fig.2.26. Digital display showing signal generated from sound reflecting of back surface

Fig.2.27. Digital display showing the presence of a reflector midway through material, with lower amplitude back surface reflector

In through-transmission two transducers located on opposing sides of the test specimen are used. One transducer acts as a transmitter, the other as a receiver. Through transmission is useful in detecting discontinuities that are not good reflectors, 2.28, 2.29.

Fig. 2.28. Digital display showing received sound through material thickness.

Fig.2.29. Digital display showing loss of received signal due to presence of discontinuity in the sound field

2- Normal and angle beam:

In normal beam testing, the sound beam is introduced into the test article at 90 degree to the surface. In angle beam testing, the sound beam is introduced into the test article at some angle other than 90 this is techniques as shown in figure 2.30. The choice between normal and angle beam inspection usually depends on two considerations:

- The orientation of the feature of interest – the sound should be directed to produce the largest reflection from the feature.
- Obstructions on the surface of the part that must be worked around.

Fig.2.30. Test techniques – normal and angle Beam

When performing an angle beam inspection, it is important to know where the sound beam is encountering an interface and reflecting. The reflection points are sometimes referred to as nodes. The location of the nodes can be obtained by using the trigonometric functions or by using the trig-based formulas which are given below. As shown in figures 2.31.

Where:

- **Nodes** - surface points where sound waves reflect.
- **Skip Distance** - surface distance of two successive nodes.
- **Leg 1 (L₁)** - sound path in material to 1st node.
- **Leg 2 (L₂)** - sound path in material from 1st to 2nd node.
- **θ_R** - refracted sound wave angle.

$$\text{SIN} = \frac{\text{OPP}}{\text{HYP}}$$

$$\text{COS} = \frac{\text{ADJ}}{\text{HYP}}$$

$$\text{TAN} = \frac{\text{OPP}}{\text{ADJ}}$$

Fig.2.31. Angle beam inspection calculations

3- Contact versus immersion:

To get useful levels of sound energy into a material, the air between the transducer and the test article must be removed. This is referred to as coupling as shown in figure 2.32. In contact testing a couplant such as water, oil or a gel is applied between the transducer and the part. In immersion testing, the part and the transducer are placed in a water bath.

Fig.2.32. Couplant

2. Equipments:

Equipment for ultrasonic testing is very diversified. Proper selection is important to insure accurate inspection data as desired for specific applications. In general, there are three basic components that comprise an ultrasonic test system:

- Transducers
- Instrumentation
- Calibration Standards

A- Transducers:

Transducers are manufactured in a variety of forms, shapes and sizes for varying applications and categorized in a number of ways which include:

- Contact or immersion
- Single or dual element
- Normal or angle beam

In selecting a transducer for a given application, it is important to choose the desired frequency, bandwidth, size, and in some cases focusing which optimizes the inspection capabilities. Type of transducers as shown in figure 2.33^[10].

Fig. 2.33. Transducers

Contact transducers are designed to withstand rigorous use, and usually have a wear plate on the bottom surface to protect the piezoelectric element from contact with the surface of the test article. Many incorporate ergonomic designs for ease of grip while scanning along the surface. This is transducer as shown in figure 2.34^[10].

Fig.2.34. Contact transducers

Contact transducers are available with two piezoelectric crystals in one housing. These transducers are called dual element transducers. One crystal acts as a transmitter, the other as a receiver. This arrangement improves near surface resolution because the second transducer does not need to complete a transmit function before listening for echoes. This is transducer as shown in figure 2.35^[10].

Fig.2.35. Dual element transducers

A way to improve near surface resolution with a single element transducer is through the use of a delay line.

Angle beam transducers incorporate wedges to introduce a refracted shear wave into a material. The incident wedge angle is used with the material velocity to determine the desired refracted shear wave according to (Snell's Law refer to Appendix I). Transducers can use fixed or variable wedge angles. Common application is in weld examination. This is transducer as shown in figure 2.36^[10].

Fig.2.36. Angle beam transducers

Immersion transducers are designed to transmit sound by the transducer and test specimen are immersed in a liquid coupling medium (usually water).

B- Instrumentation:

Ultrasonic equipment is usually purchased to satisfy specific inspection needs, some users may purchase general purpose equipment to fulfill a number of inspection applications. Test equipment can be classified in a number of different ways, this may include portable or stationary, contact or immersion, manual or automated. Further classification of instruments commonly divides them into four general categories: D- meters, Flaw detectors, Industrial and special application. **D-meters or digital thickness gauge instruments** as shown in figure 2.37 provide the user with a digital (numeric) readout. They are designed primarily for corrosion/erosion inspection applications^[12].

Fig.2.37. D-meters or digital thickness gauge instruments

Some instruments provide the user with both a digital readout and a display of the signal, as shown in figure 2.38. A distinct advantage of these units is that they allow the user to evaluate the signal to ensure that the digital measurements are of the desired features. **Flaw detectors** are instruments designed primarily for the inspection of components for defects. However, the signal can be evaluated to obtain other information such as material thickness values. Both analog and digital display. Offer the user options of gating horizontal sweep and amplitude threshold ^[12].

Fig.2.38. Flaw detectors

Immersion ultrasonic scanning systems are used for automated data acquisition and imaging. Images of a quarter produced with an ultrasonic immersion scanning system shown in figure 2.39^[10].

Gray scale image produced using the sound reflected from the front surface of the coin

Gray scale image produced using the sound reflected from the back surface of the coin (inspected from “heads” side)

Fig.2.39. Ultrasonic immersion scanning system

C- Calibration standards:

Calibration is a operation of configuring the ultrasonic test equipment to known values. This provides the inspector with a means of comparing test signals to known measurements. Calibration standards are typically manufactured from materials of the same acoustic properties as those of the test articles. The following provide examples of specific types of standards. This is Calibration as shown in figures 2.40 and 2.41 [12].

Fig.2.40. Thickness calibration standards and distance/area amplitude standards

Fig.2.41. Angle beam inspections

1- Data presentation:

Information from ultrasonic testing can be presented in a number of differing formats. Three of the more common formats include [12]:

i- *Data Presentation - A-scan:*

A-scan presentation displays the amount of received ultrasonic energy as a function of time. Relative discontinuity size can be estimated by comparing the signal amplitude to that from a known reflector. Reflector depth can be determined by the position of the signal on the horizontal sweep this is as shown in figure 2.42 [10].

Fig.2.42. Data presentation - A-scan

ii- Data Presentation - B-scan:

Presentation technique displaying data in a cross-sectional view.

iii- Data Presentation - C-scan:

Presentation technique that displays specimen data in a plan type view.

2- Attenuation ^[12]:

This is the loss of ultrasound as a medium is traversed. It occurs due to absorption of ultrasound energy by conversion to heat, as well as reflection, refraction and scattering. Attenuation is increased (and hence penetration of the beam reduced) by:-

- Increased distance from the transducer
- Less homogenous medium to traverse due to increased acoustic impedance mismatch
- Higher frequency (shorter wavelength) transducers
- Air forms a virtually impenetrable barrier to ultrasound, while fluid offers the least resistance.

3. **Application of the method:**

Some of the applications for which ultrasonic testing may be employed include:

- Flaw detection (cracks, inclusions, porosity, etc.)
- Erosion & corrosion thickness gauging
- Estimation of void content in composites and plastics
- Measurement of case hardening depth in steels
- Estimation of grain size in metals

2.3.4. Principles of eddy-current testing:

The definition of eddy current is electric currents induced within conductors by a changing magnetic field in the conductor. Eddy current theory is based on the principles of electricity and magnetism (Electromagnetism) particularly the inductive properties of alternating current.

In 1831, an Englishman, Michael Faraday, discovered electromagnetic induction, it wasn't until the last few decades of the twentieth century after portable eddy current appeared^[2].

The eddy current testing method has advantages as^[14]:

- Portable and moderate cost
- Sensitive to small indications and immediate results can be gotten.
- Little part preparation

Also the method has limitations or disadvantages:

- Essentially a surface inspection
- Surface to be inspected must be accessible to contact by the eddy current probe
- Rough surfaces interface with test sensitivity
- Suitable for inspection of metals only
- No permanent test records
- Considerable skill and familiarity required in handling test equipment
- Time consuming to scan large areas

1. Physics of the method:

The physics of the method is depending on the following points :

A- Principle of electromagnetism:

Is the phenomenon whereby the passage of electrons through a conductor causes a magnetic field to develop concentrically around the conductor, perpendicular to its axis. A concentrated magnetic field, similar to that obtained from a bar magnet, can be obtained by winding a conductor into a coil as shown in figure 2.43^[2].

Fig.2.43. The two effects can be shown in a simple transformer

A coil functioning as an electromagnet is called a solenoid, although an ideal solenoid has a length much greater than its diameter. A solenoid concentrates a magnetic field inside the coil, with

opposing poles at each end of the coil, and flux lines completely encircling the loops of the coil. If direct current is applied to the coil, its magnetic field will flow in only one direction and it can perform the same work of attracting ferromagnetic materials as a permanent magnet. In addition, the coil can be wound around a ferromagnetic core for increased field strength. If the current is alternating, the electromagnetic field will likewise alternate and the coil will exhibit a quality called inductance, L , whose unit is the henry. Inductance is the ability of a conductor to induce voltage in itself or in a neighboring conductor when the current varies^[2].

B- Electromagnetic induction^[2]:

The induction process will first be modeled using a pair of coils as primary and secondary elements of a mutual induction circuit. Sinusoids are included to illustrate time and polarity relationships, where a single coil is the primary circuit and the test material is the secondary as shown in figure 2.44 .

Fig.2.44. Showing the single coil and the test material

C- Basic eddy Current testing^[13]:

Simple Coil above a metal surface: when an AC current flows in a coil in close proximity to a conducting surface the magnetic field of the coil will induce circulating (eddy) currents in that surface. The magnitude and phase of the eddy currents will affect the loading on the coil and thus its impedance. See figure 2.45.

Fig.2.45. Simple coil above a metal surface

As an example, assume that there is a deep crack in the surface immediately underneath the coil. This will interrupt or reduce the eddy current flow, thus decreasing the loading on the coil and increasing its effective impedance. See figure 2.46.

Fig. 2.46. The deep crack on the surface

This is the basis of eddy current testing, by monitoring the voltage across the coil in such an arrangement we can detect changes in the material of interest.

Fig.2.47. Monitoring the voltage across the coil

Note that cracks must interrupt the surface eddy current flow to be detected. Cracks lying parallel to the current path will not cause any significant interruption and may not be detected, See figure 2.48.

Fig.2.48. Parallel and perpendicular cracks detection

D- Eddy current flow characteristics^[2]:

Eddy currents have a number of flow characteristics that affect their test performance:

- i. They flow only in closed, concentric loops.
- ii. The flow paths are parallel to the turns of the bobbin-type coil in shown Figure 2.49. and perpendicular to the axis of the coil's flux field.

Fig.2.49. Bobbin-type coil's flux and eddy currents

- iii. The orientation of the coil to the test material therefore determines the orientation of the eddy current flow pattern in the test material.
- iv. Discontinuities are detectable by the eddy current method in proportion to the degree to which they disturb the flow pattern. Thus, a discontinuity is least detectable when its longest dimension is parallel to eddy current flow paths (see figure 2.50).

Fig.2.50. Discontinuities in eddy current flow patterns. (a) Discontinuity parallel to flow paths. (b) Discontinuity perpendicular to flow paths.

- v. Eddy currents behave like compressible fluids. (see figure 2.51).

Fig.2.51 Eddy currents compressed by material boundaries

- vi. Since an alternating flux field develops eddy currents, their flow in the test material likewise alternates clockwise and counterclockwise.
- vii. Eddy current density varies in the test material. Standard depth of penetration in English and metric units for a particular material and test frequency can be calculated as follows :

$\delta(\text{inches}) = 1.98 \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{f \times \mu_r}}$ $\delta(\text{mm}) = 25 \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{f \times \mu_r}}$	<p>Where:</p> <p>δ = standard depth of penetration</p> <p>ρ = resistivity</p> <p>f = frequency</p> <p>μ_r = relative permeability</p>
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E- Factors affecting eddy current response:

A number of factors, apart from flaws, will affect the eddy current response from a probe^[2]. (commonly conducting material). The density and spatial patterns of these eddy currents (and hence of the magnetic field that they produce) depends on the material properties (permittivity, conductivity and permeability) coil geometry and frequency^[7], The main factors are:

1- Material conductivity^[13]:

The conductivity of a material has a very direct effect on the eddy current flow: the greater the conductivity of a material the greater the flow of eddy currents on the surface. conductivity is shown in table 2.14^[2].

Table (2.14): Typical depth of penetration and conductivity.

Metal	Conductivity % IACS	Resistivity	Permeability	36.8% Depth of penetration					
				1KHz	4KHz	16KHz	64KHz	256KHz	1MHz
Copper	100	1.7	1	0.082	0.041	0.021	0.010	0.005	0.0026
6061 T-6	42	4.1	1	0.126	0.063	0.032	0.016	0.008	0.004
7075 T-6	32	5.3	1	0.144	0.072	0.036	0.018	0.009	0.0046
Magnesium	37	4.6	1	0.134	0.067	0.034	0.017	0.008	0.0042
Lead	7.8	22	1	0.292	0.146	0.073	0.37	0.018	0.0092
Uranium	6.0	29	1	0.334	0.167	0.084	0.042	0.021	0.0106
Zirconium	3.4	70	1.02	0.516	0.258	0.129	0.065	0.032	0.0164
Steel	2.9	60	750	0.019	0.0095	0.0048	0.0024	0.0012	0.0006
Cast steel	10.7	16	175	0.018	0.0089	0.0044	0.0022	0.0011	0.0006

2- Permeability^[13]:

This may be described as the ease with which a material can be magnetized. For non-ferrous metals such as copper, brass, aluminum etc., and for austenitic stainless steels the permeability is the same as that of ‘free space’, i.e. the relative permeability(μ_r) is one. For ferrous metals however the value of μ_r may be several hundred.

3- Frequency^[13]:

As we will discuss, eddy current response is greatly affected by the test frequency chosen, fortunately this is one property we can control.

4- Geometry^[13]:

In a real part, for example one which is not flat or of infinite size, Geometrical features such as curvature, edges, grooves etc. will exist and will effects the eddy current response.

Fig.2.52. (a)Shows how is the effect on of edges on the, (b)shows the effect of edge on screen ED waves

5- Proximity / Lift-off^[13]:

The closer a probe coil is to the surface the greater will be the effect on that coil. This has two main effects:

- a. The “lift-off” signal as the probe is moved on and off the surface.
- b. A reduction in sensitivity as the coil to product spacing Increases.

6- Depth of Penetration^[13]:

The eddy current density, and thus the strength of the response from a flaw, is greatest on the surface of the metal being tested and declines with depth. It is mathematically convenient to define the “standard depth of penetration” where the eddy current is $1/e$ (37%) of its surface value as shown in fig.2.53.

Fig.2.53. Depth of penetration

From this it can be seen that depth of penetration:

- a. Decreases with an increase in frequency.
- b. Decreases with an increase in conductivity.
- c. Decreases with an increase in permeability - This can be very significant - penetration into ferrous materials at practical frequencies is very small. And that is shown on figure 2.54^[1], and table 2.14.

Fig.2.54. The graph shows the effect of frequency on standard depth of penetration

2. Equipments:

Equipments in Eddy current inspection is very important due to the number of applications, . In general, there are three basic components that comprise an ultrasonic test system:

A- *Instrumentation*^[7]:

1- Eddy current instruments:

Eddy current instruments can be purchased in a large variety of configurations. Both analog and digital instruments are available. Instruments are commonly classified by the type of display used to present the data. The common display types are analog meter, digital readout, impedance plane and time versus signal amplitude. Some instruments are capable of presenting data in several display formats. See (figures 2.55,2.56)

Fig.2.55. Instrument model E400

Fig.2.56. Portable defectometer

2- Resonant circuits^[7]:

Eddy current probes typically have a frequency or a range of frequencies that they are designed to operate. When the probe is operated outside of this range, problems with the data can occur. When a probe is operated at too high of a frequency, resonance can occur in the circuit.

B- Probes^[7]:

Eddy current probes are available in a large variety of shapes and sizes. In fact, one of the major advantages of eddy current inspection is that probes can be custom designed for a wide variety of applications, that is shown in figure 2.57.

Fig.2.57. Probes

1- Probes - Mode of operation^[7]:

The mode of operation of a probe generally falls into one of four categories: absolute, differential, reflection and hybrid. Each of these classifications will be discussed in more detail below.

<p>Absolute Probes</p> <p>Absolute probes generally have a single test coil that is used to generate the eddy currents and sense changes in the eddy current field.</p>	<p>Differential Probes</p> <p>Differential probes have two active coils usually wound in opposition, although they could be wound in addition with similar results.</p>
--	--

Fig.5.58.Absolute probe

Fig.5.59.Differential probes

Reflection Probes

Reflection probes have two coils similar to a differential probe, but one coil is used to excite the eddy currents and the other is used to sense changes in the test material.

Fig.2.60. Reflection probe

Hybrid Probes

An example of a hybrid probe is the split D, differential probe shown to the right.

Fig.2.61. D probe

2- Probes – Configurations^[7]:

Some of the common classifications of probes based on their configuration include surface probes, bolt hole probes, inside diameter (ID) probes, and outside diameter (OD) probes.

Surface Probes

Surface probes are usually designed to be handheld and are intended to be used in contact with the test surface.

Fig.2.62. Surface probe

Bolt Hole Probes

Bolt hole probes are a special type of surface probe that is designed to be used with a bolt hole scanner.

Fig2.63. Bolt hole probe

ID or Bobbin Probes

ID probes, which are also referred to as Bobbin probes or feed through probes, are inserted into hollow products, such as pipes, to inspect from the inside out. See

Fig.2.64. ID probe

OD or Encircling Coils

OD probes are often called encircling coils. They are similar to ID probes except that the coil(s) encircle the material to inspect from the outside in.

Fig.2.65.OD coils

C- Calibration^[2]:

Test calibration or standardization is the process of adjusting the instrument display to represent a known reference standard so that the test can be a comparison between the test material and the reference standard. Moreover, the test system should be checked at regular intervals against the reference standard to ensure that it is operating properly and is still set up correctly for the test being performed. If a variation in instrument performance or setup is discovered, all material tested since the last verification of proper performance and setup should be retested.

The following rules apply to the selection and fabrication of standards:

- i. The test standard should be of the same material, with the same wall thickness and configuration, and receive the same processing as the material to be tested.
- ii. The artificial discontinuities in the standard should model the natural discontinuities expected in the test material. For example:

Fig.2.66. Inspection of heat exchanger tubing.

- Drilled holes can simulate pits .see figure 2.66.
- EDM notches or saw cuts can simulate cracks.

- Thickness reduction in tubing can simulate wear.
 - Heat Treatment can simulate a conductivity change.
- iii. Artificial discontinuities in test standards should be sufficiently separated so that their signals will not interfere with each other.
- iv. Standards should contain no discontinuities other than those intended to produce reference signals. Figure 2.67 shows tubing standards as well as standards used to calibrate eddy current instruments for detection and evaluation of cracks in material surfaces and inside bolt holes. To augment standards containing artificial discontinuities, it is helpful to build a library of natural discontinuities by obtaining actual specimens removed from.

Fig.2.67.Reference standards.

3. Application of the method^[2]:

The versatility of the eddy current method has resulted in broad applications usage. However, the major application areas include the following:

- In-service inspection of tubing at nuclear and fossil fuel power utilities, at chemical. and petrochemical plants, on nuclear submarines, and in air conditioning systems.
- Inspection of aerospace structures and engines.
- Production testing of tubing, pipe, wire, rod, and bar stock.

Chapter 3
The Practical Part

Work in our project has been done on three destinations and this is shown in the following flow chart :

3.1. Data Collection:

The data collected in this project is depended on two ways that is illustrated as following :

3.1.1. Books:

Books and Handbooks was the first reference in the project, due to the extension of these references and the quantum information .

3.1.2 Website:

The trustworthy websites of the NDT was chosen in this project which refers to the international organizations and companies.

3.2. Analysis:

One of the most important procedures in this project is data analyzing and the taken way to introduce that with understandably not obscurity, so the analysis is concentrated on the following two points :

3.2.1 Choosing of methods:

The methods of inspection that are chosen is :

1. The Penetrant method.
2. Magnetic particle method.
3. Ultrasonic method.
4. Eddy current method.

3.2.2. Data reduction:

The data on this project is depending on the instruments and operations availability for the chosen methods in the locations we worked in (Al-Heswa station and Sana'a International Airport).

3.3. The Experiments:

3.3.1 Safety¹:

Before we do any inspection experiment we should take in consider the following notes :

- Electric Shock and Burns—Electric short circuits can cause shock and particularly burns from the high amperages at relatively low voltages that are used. Equipment handling water suspensions should have good electrical grounds.
- Flying Particles—Magnetic particles, particularly the dry ones, dirt, foundry sand, rust, and mill scale can enter the eyes and ears when they are blown off the part when applying them to a vertical or overhead surface or when cleaning an examined surface with compressed air.
- Falls—A fall from a scaffold or ladder if working on a large structure in the field or shop.
- Fire—Ignition of a petroleum distillate bath.
- Environment—Doing magnetic particle examination where flammable vapors are present as in a petrochemical plant or oil refinery. Underwater work has its own set of hazards and should be addressed independently.
- Wet Floors—Slipping on a floor wetted with a particle suspension.
- Shifting or Dropping of Large Components—Large components, especially those on temporary supports can shift during examination or fall while being lifted. In addition, operators should be alert to the possibility of injury to body members being caught beneath a sling/chain or between head/tail stock and the piece.

- Ultraviolet Light Exposure—Ultraviolet light can adversely affect the eyes and skin. Safety goggles designed to absorb UV wavelength radiation are suggested where high intensity black light is used.
- Equipment Hazards—Because of the large breadth of equipment available, unique safety hazards may exist and should be addressed for each case individually.

3.3.2 Verification:

Verification is considered here for the Penetrant and Magnetic particle methods .

Table (3.1)^[8]: Required Verification Intervals

Item	Maximum Time Between Verification ^A
Lighting: ^B	
- Visible light intensity	Weekly
- Ambient light intensity	Weekly
- Black light intensity	Daily
System Performance: ^B	Daily
Wet particle concentration	8 hours, or every shift change
Wet particle contamination: ^B	1 week
Water break test	Daily
Equipment calibration check: ^B	
- Ammeter accuracy	6 months
- Timer control	6 months
- Quick break	6 months
- Yoke dead weight check	6 months
- Black and white light meters	6 months
- Gaussmeter accuracy	6 months

^A When the inspection system is in operation.

^B The maximum time between verifications may be reduced or extended when substantiated by actual technical/reliability data.

3.3.3. Liquid penetrant experiments:

Many liquid penetrant inspections were done and the certificate below of the OJT (On Job Training) illustrate the list of liquid penetrant inspections:

اليمنية Maintenance & Engineering NDT Work Shop		NDT Inspection Log Records				
Name: SAMER.SAMEER.ABDULLA : Level II CAMA Lic #. NDT-PC #..... Methods <i>P.T.</i> <i>AHMAD HAYEL</i>						
Date	A/C Reg.	Job No. SSI	Task Details	NDT Method	Time/Findings/Remarks	Initial
23/09/2013	A 310	32-02	Main Break Assy S/N 4 1753	PT	1/2 hr, ϕ	
24/09/2013	A 310	32-001	M/W Assy S/N 37214, 36642	PT	2 hr, ϕ	
25/09/2013	A 330	32-003	Main wheel Assy S/N 2978	PT	2 hr, ϕ	
25/09/2013	A 330	32-003	M/W Assy Bolts (22EA) S/N 2978	PT	2 hr, ϕ	
24/09/2013	A 310	32-001	M/W Assy S/N 3715/36562	ET	1 hr, ϕ	
Senior Manager, Quality Assurance: <i>Nazek M. Algora</i> Signature:						

We will explain in details two inspection experiments, one in Al-Heswa thermal power station and desalination complex– Aden, and the other one in Sana'a International Airport.

1. Experiment (1): test in the welding of two pipes:

Fig.3.1. Welding of two pipes

Aim: To inspect the welding of two pipes by liquid penetrant testing method, to find any defects.

Procedures:

- 1- Clean the surface of the pipes to be welded.
- 2- Make a chamfer at 45 degree and two spot between the surfaces of the two pipes.

Fig.3.2. Clean the surface of the pipes and Make a chamfer

- 3- Welding the rest of the two pipes (fully).

Fig.3.3. Welding of pipes

- 4- Grinding and removing the additional welding.

Fig.3.4. Grinding to the welding

- 5- Clean the welded surface by cleaner.

Fig.3.5. clean by cleaner

- 6- Apply the penetrant in the welding of two pipes.

Fig.3.6. Apply the penetrant

7- Penetrant dwell in the weld

Fig.3.7. Penetrant dwell

8- Remove excess penetrant.

9- Apply a developer

Fig.3.8. Remove penetrant and apply a developer

10- Indication development

Fig.3.9. Indication development

11- Clean the surfaces of welding

Fig.3.10. Clean the surfaces

12- Return the steps 3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 and 11 to make another layer of welding.

2. Experiment (2): test of the wheel A330:

Fig.3.11. Wheel of A330

Aim: To inspect the wheel A330 by liquid penetrant testing (water washable) method , to find any defects.

Procedures:

1- Put the wheel in the tank of penetrant.

Fig.3.12. penetrant

2- Apply a dwell time (25 min.).

Fig.3.13. Apply a dwell

3- Exit the wheel from the tank of the penetrant.

Fig.3.14. Exit the wheel

4- Dry the wheel from the penetrant by normal air.

5- Remove the excess penetrant by water removal.

Fig.3.15. Normal air and water removal

6- Dry the wheel from the water by using a dryer.

Fig.3.16. Dryer

7- Apply a dye developer at a dark area.

Fig.3.17. Darken area

8- Using an ultraviolet light to inspect the cracks

Fig.3.18. Ultraviolet light

9- Clean the wheel exactly.

Fig.3.19. Wheel is cleaned

10- Writing a report.

3.3.4. Magnetic particle experiments:

Many magnetic particle inspections were done and the certificate below of the OJT (On Job Training) illustrate the list of magnetic particle inspections:

		<h2 style="text-align: center;">NDT Inspection Log Records</h2>				
Name: SAMEER.SAMEER.ABDULRA-LEVEL IICAMA Lic #. NDT-PC #..... Methods <i>MPI</i> HMAN HAYEL						
Date	A/C Reg.	Job No. SSI	Task Details	NDT Method	Time/Findings/Remarks	Initial
24/09/2013	A310	32-001	M/W BOLTS (18EA) S/N 36642	MPI	1/2 hr, ϕ	
1/10/2013	A310-ADR	575146-01-1	Spoiled 1 And 2 Hinge Zone (572)	MPI	1/2 hr, ϕ	
1/10/2013	A320-ADR	575146-01-1	Spoiled 1 And 2 Hinge Zone (572)	MPI	1/2 hr, ϕ	
5/10/2013	A320	328502	BOLTS (18EA) S/N 46225	MPI	1/2 hr, ϕ	
5/10/2013	A320	328502	BOLTS (18EA) S/N 46642	MPI	1/2 hr, ϕ	
Senior Manager, Quality Assurance: <i>Nazek M. Al-Jena</i> Signature:						

We will explain in details two inspection experiments, all of this experiments happen in Sana'a International Airport:

1. Experiment (1): A310 airbus spoiler:

Fig.3.20. A310 airbus spoiler

Aim: To inspect the spoiler by magnetic particles inspection method , to find any defects.

Procedures:

- 1- The brake shop bring the spoiler clean and ready to be inspected, so no need for part preparation.
- 2- The properties of the method we use:
 - a- Bench unit machine for magnetizing the part.
 - b- Circular magnetization.
 - c- Indirect method , using a bar passing through the spoiler, as shown in the figure below.
 - d- Continuous method, using FWDC.

Fig.3.21. Place the specimen at the bench unit

- 3- Type of the medium is magnetic particles suspension (kerosene + particles powder), fluorescent type.
- 4- Apply suspension to the part after we check its concentration level by steps shown below, the required settling volume is from(0.1 to 0.4 mL) in a 100-mL bath sample:

- 1 AGITATE THE SUSPENSION THOROUGHLY TO ASSURE PARTICLE DISTRIBUTION
- 2 FILL 100cc (100 ML) SAMPLE FROM THE DELIVERY HOSE INTO A 100cc (100 ML) GRADUATED CENTRIFUGE TUBE OR GRADUATE.

3. PLACE CENTRIFUGE IN STAND

- 4 DEMAGNETIZE, IF NECESSARY (IF CLUMPING OCCURS).

- 5 ALLOW TO SETTLE FOR 30 MINUTES.
- 6 TAKE READING AND RECORD IN THE LOG.
- 7 ADJUST BATH EITHER BY ADDING PARTICLES OR VEHICLE AS NECESSARY.

Fig.3.22. Settling testing

- 5- We magnetize the part by one shot while the suspension is applied to the surface, then we inspect it by the ultraviolet light in dark room.
- 6- We rotate the spoiler 180 degree and repeat the previous step, to cover the whole surface of the spoiler.

Fig.3.23. inspecting in dark room

7- After the inspection we demagnetize the part by passing it through demagnetizing machine.

Fig.3.24. Demagnetize the part

8- Check the magnetic field in the part if it vanished or not by gaussmeter as shown below , if there is a magnetic field we pass it again through the machine until it vanish.

Fig.3.25. check the magnetic field

9- Cleaning the part from the medium we applied on it by a compressed air and water as shown below.

Fig.3.26. Clean the part

2. **Experiment (2): A320 bolts (18EA):**

Fig.3.27. A320 bolts (18EA)

Aim: To inspect the group of bolts by magnetic particles inspection method , to find any defects.

Procedures:

- 1- For cleaning the bolts dirt and grease use a cleaning machine which heat and vibrate the cleaner solvent (we used magna Vu cleaner).

Fig.3.28. Prepare the cleaning machine

2- Then we immerse the bolts in the cleaning solvent and adjust the setting of the cleaning machine at 40 C temperature degree and vibration state, cover the cleaning machine and leave it from (10-20 min.).

Fig.3.29. Put the parts in the cleaning machine

3- After the pre-cleaning we do a post-cleaning by brushing the bolts and washing it by the water-air nozzle as shown below.

Fig.3.30. Washing and post clean the parts

- 4- Then we start the process of magnetization and applying the medium by:
- a- Bench unit machine for magnetizing the part.
 - b- Longitudinal magnetization.
 - c- Indirect method , using a coil passing through the bolt, as shown in the figure below.
 - d- Continuous method, using AC current.

Fig.3.31. Place the part at the magnetizing machine

5- After that we inspect the bolts in dark room by ultraviolet light.

Fig.3.32. Inspect the part in dark room

6- After the inspection , we demagnetize the parts by small demagnetizing machine which is used for small parts like bolts. Pass each bolt individually in the machine.

Fig.3.33. Demagnetize the parts

7- Finally post-cleaning after inspection to remove remnants of the magnetic particles clinging to the surface by the compressed air and water.

Fig.3.34. Cleaning the parts

3.3.5 . Ultrasonic experiments:

We will explain in details two inspection experiments in Al-Heswa thermal power station and desalination complex– Aden.

1. Experiment (1): Thickness gauge instrument (DM2E):

Fig.3.35. Digital thickness gauge instrument (DM2E)

Aim: To inspect the pipes by ultrasonic inspection method , to find the thickness of pipes.

Procedures:

- 1- Press "CAL" key and couple probe to built-in probe zero(PO) block until a row of dashes.
- 2- replaces the PO display.
- 3- Couple probe to a calibration standard of known thickness and same material as that to be tested.
- 4- Obtain stable reading, uncouple probe, and wipe any excess couplant from probe face.
- 5- Using the UP and DOWN arrow keys, increase or decrease the displayed value to match the thickness of the calibration standard.
- 6- Press "CAL" key again and start taking thickness measurements.

A- The keyboard of the instrument:

- 1- On / Off key:

Pressing this key will turn on or turn off the equipment.

2- Cal key:

The CAL key has two purposes:

- i- With the measuring display on, CAL key allows calibration of the equipment to take measurements on steel.*

How to perform the calibration? (This is calibration as shown in figure 2.48).

- Put couplant gel on the calibration disk (PO)
- Press the transducer against the calibration disk.
- Wait till the measurement becomes stable, and after this press key CAL.
- The instrument should then display $0.250'' \pm 0.001''$ ($6.35\text{mm} \pm 0.01$). If not,
- calibrate again by pressing CAL.
- When attained, the equipment is ready to measure on Steel.

- ii- The other purpose of the CAL key is activated within the configuration options and will allow entering the different menus, and to confirm modifications made to the configuration parameters.*

3- Up and Down Keys:

The Up and Down keys will allow modification of the values to be edited, within the different configuration options.

One of the most important cases we faced during our practical in the power station, is when the tubes of one boiler exploded.

Here we will mention the steps that the inspector do in this case:

- 1- The surfaces of the tubes near the exploded location are subject to ultrasonic testing should be free from any existing lubricants, dirt, residue, rust and sharp edges...etc.
- 2- Put couplant gel on the tubes.
- 3- Inspect the tubes by measuring the thickness of these tubes (expected thickness 4-3 mm).
- 4- If we find tubes that have less thickness than 3mm, mark them.
- 5- After that another welding group will come and cut the defected part and replace it by a suitable one by welding, and he will do his inspection again after welding and he told as if irregularities are found he will order to grind this part to make the surface smooth, i.e. to avoid irregularities (stress raisers). This is case as shown in figures 2.36.

Fig.3.36: Tubes of one boiler exploded

2. Experiment (2): Flaw detectors instrument (USK 7S)

Fig.3.37. Flaw detectors instrument (USK 7S)

Aim: To inspect the material by ultrasonic inspection method , to find the thickness of material and the defects.

Procedures:

- 1- TR-switch on.
- 2- dB- switch coarse ~ 40dB.
- 3- Test range control.
- 4- Adjusting range.
- 5- dB-switch fine + dB divider adjusting 80 %.

A- The keyboard of the instrument:

- 1- Battery check meter (BATT)
- 2- Pulse shift control
- 3- Test range control, fine
- 4- dB-switch, fine
- 5- Suppression control
- 6- Focus control (FOC)
- 7- Monitor gate control (gate width)
- 8- Monitor gate control (gate start)
- 9- Charging socket for monitor output

- 10- Probe cable socket (receiver)
- 11- Probe cable socket (transmitter)
- 12- Test range control, coarse
- 13- dB-switch, coarse
- 14- ON-/OFF-; TR-switch(Pulse strength)
- 15- db-divider, fine
- 16- Visual monitor signal
- 17- Reject alarm
- 18- Glam ping mount for front scale

The keyboard of the instrument (USK 7S) as shown in figure 2.38.

Fig.3.38. The keyboard of the instrument (USK 7S)

For calibration of the instrument for specified test range, it is necessary to fulfill the following steps:

1. The type of material to be tested should be known.
2. fix the required test range , for example if the material to be tested has a thickness of 80 mm then it is better to calibrate on a range of 100 mm.
3. The presence of calibration block (supplied with the instrument) of the same piece under the test, the thickness of the calibration block must be known.
4. Decide the required scale factor, i-e to know in each how many mm division in the screen from 1-10.
5. Fix the position of each pulse from the used pulses in the calibration on the numbered lines on the screen (screen division lines).

Example(1):-

Calibrate the instrument to test a piece of (Iron) by using the probe MP4F ?

Solution:

Test range =100 mm

Type of instrument- USK 7S

Name of probe- MP4F

Calibration block- V_{II} with 25 mm thickness

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Number of pulses required for calibration} &= \frac{\text{Test range}}{\text{Thickness of the calibration block}} = \\ &= \frac{100 \text{ mm}}{25 \text{ mm}} = 4 \text{ pulses} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Scale factor} = \frac{\text{Test range}}{\text{Number of instrument division}} = \frac{100 \text{ mm}}{10 \text{ divisions}} = 10 \text{ mm in each division}$$

Because the distance between each two pluses represents the thickness of the calibration block is 25 mm then the first pulse is equivalent block to thickness 25 mm and the second is 50 mm and the third is 75, the fourth is 100 mm. the calibration processes (method) must-but each pulse from the four pulses in it exact place on the screen as follows :

$$\text{Position of the first pulse} = \frac{\text{Thickness which represented by the pulse}}{\text{Scale factor}} = \frac{25\text{mm}}{10 \text{ mm}} = 2.5, \text{ which represent the division 2.5 in the screen.}$$

$$\text{Position of the second pulse} = \frac{50\text{mm}}{10\text{mm}} = 5, \text{ which represent the division 5 in the screen.}$$

$$\text{Position of the third pulse} = \frac{75\text{mm}}{10\text{mm}} = 7.5, \text{ which represent the division 7.5 in the screen.}$$

$$\text{Position of the fourth pulse} = \frac{100\text{mm}}{10\text{mm}} = 10, \text{ which represent the division 10 in the screen.}$$

The following steps show how the practical calibration process is made:

The instrument is switched on and probe is connected to it by the suitable cable.

1. Put the probe on the calibration block.
2. By using the control keys which are specially mode for the calibration process, we do the following four steps, on the screen which is divided gradually in lower end from 0to 10.
 - i. Put the first pulse on the division 2.5.
 - ii. Put the second pulse on the division 5.
 - iii. Put the third pulse on the division 7.5.
 - iv. Put the fourth pulse on the division 10.

And the position of the four pulses are as shown in figure 2.39, below it means the calibration process has been done precisely and instrument is now ready to be used on a test a maximum range of 100mm in iron.

Fig.3.39. Position of the four pulses in the screen

Example (2):-

After calibration of the instrument in example (1) for attest range of 100 mm, it is required to test too iron pieces shown in figures 2.39 , 2.40 and 2.41 to measure their thickness and to be sure that they are free of defects.

Solution :

- a- When the probe is put on the first iron piece, the result of test was as shown in figure 2.40. in addition to occurrence of the initial (transmitted) pulse to the left of the screen just a little bit before zero, another pulse occurred on the right side of the initial pulse on division 8 from division of the screen. The distance between the initial pulse and the second pulse is the distance between the two surfaces of the piece, i-e the piece thickness and it is shown that there are no any other pulses existed between these two pulses which means this piece is free of defects. Now how can we calculate the thickness of iron piece ?

The thickness of the iron piece = *The reading of place position on the screen* × *Scale factur*

$$= 8 \times 10 \text{ (Scale factor in mm) } = 80 \text{ mm .}$$

Fig.3.40. Piece without any defects

b- When the probes is put on the second iron piece the result was as shown in figure 2.41. In addition to the initial pulse, another two pulses were on the screen, the first one was on division 4 and the second one was on division 8 and it is longer than the first one. The first on pulse shows that there is a defect (crack or notch) and the distance between it and the initial pulse is the distance between it and the surface of the piece. The second pulse which is the larger one and represents the thickness of the iron piece and is equal the distance between it and the initial pulse. The result are shown as calculated below.

Defect position in depth of iron piece reading on the screen \times scale factor

$$= 4 \times 10 = 40 \text{ mm .}$$

Thickness of the iron piece = $8 \times 10 = 80 \text{ mm.}$

Fig.3.41. piece with defect

3.3.6. Eddy current experiments:

Many eddy current inspections were done and the certificate below of the OJT (On Job Training) illustrate the list of eddy current inspections:

		<h2 style="text-align: center;">NDT Inspection Log Records</h2>				
Name: <u>SAMIER.SAMEER.ABDURAH-LEVEL II</u>CAMA Lic #. NDT-PC #..... Methods <u>ET</u> <u>MAN HAYEL</u>						
Date	A/C Reg.	Job No. SSI	Task Details	NDT Method	Time/Findings/Remarks	Initial
17/09/2013	A330	32-003	M/W SIN ASSY 2728	ET	1 hr, ϕ	
19/09/2013	A310	32-003	M/W SIN ASSY W1217	ET	1/2 hr, ϕ	
23/09/2013	A320	328502	M/W SIN ASSY 4675, 52102	ET	1 hr, ϕ	
29/09/2013	A330	32-003	M/W SIN ASSY 2758	ET	1 hr, ϕ	
30/09/2013	A330	32-003	M/W SIN ASSY 25847	ET	1/2 hr, ϕ	
Senior Manager, Quality Assurance: <u>N. Alghamdi</u> Signature:						

We will explain in details one inspection experiment happen in Sana'a International Airport:

1. Experiment (1): Airbus wheel A310:

Fig.3.42. Airbus wheel A310

Aim: to inspect the stress points(near bolt holes) on the wheel by eddy current and find the defects.

Procedures:

- 1- knowledge of probable defect type, position, and orientation and here we have surface cracks.

Fig.3.43. The suitable probe

- 2- Selection of the proper probe. The probe should fit the geometry of the part and the coil must produce eddy currents that will be disrupted by the flaw
- 3- Adjusting and calibration of the instrument as following:
 - a- the probe corresponding to the type of material to be tested is plugged into the instrument.

Fig.3.44. Probe is plugged into the instrument

b- turn the instrument on.

Fig.3.45. Showing the button on/off

c- the operation mode (Aust, NFe or Fe) is selected according to material type. In this experiment the NFe "for other non-ferrous metals" is chosen due to the material of the wheel.

Fig.3.46. The NFe standard position on the instrument

d- the probe is compensated in air (lift-off),we press left off button while probe in air see figure (3.46 a) Then the probe is placed on the corresponding crack standard.

Crack Standard NFe see figure (3.46 b, c).

NOTE : $ND=0.2/0.5/1$,where ND is notch depth in millimeter .

We chose the maximum notch depth standard here 1mm and more "*as the standard of the airbus based*".

e- the zero compensation is performed in same time that probe on the chosen crack standard

To set the instrument on the required notch depth, See figure (3.46 d).

Fig .3.47. To set the instrument (a) The left off button (b)The maximum NFe standard crack that the probe must be put in(c)The probe on the NFe standard crack(d)The zero compensation button

f- The operator can choose between three alternatives for signal display on the LCD, depending on personal preference. The first display mode simulates a horizontally moving needle. The second mode shows the signal as a horizontally moving paragraph.

The third mode displays the signal amplitude as a function of time, similar to an oscilloscope.

- 4- Now we go and check the wheel by putting the probe perpendicular 'nearly 90° ' to the desired place on the specimen.
- 5- we make an alternative motion up and down to make sure if there is a crack.
- 6- if there is a crack approaching the set depth or close to it ,alarming sound will be heard and the needle will move on the screen , we can freeze the result by pressing freeze button.

Fig.3.48. Showing the needle sign and the freeze button

- 7- the result is able to be printed . by pressing copy while it is connected to the printer.

3.3.7. Evaluation:

Table (2.2)^{1]}: Types of indications

Relevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relevant indications are produced by leakage fields which are the result of discontinuities. - Relevant indications require evaluation with regard to the acceptance standards agreed upon between the manufacturer/ test agency and the purchaser.
Non-relevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-relevant indications can occur singly or in patterns as a result of leakage fields created by conditions that require no evaluation such as changes in section (like keyways and drilled holes), inherent material properties (like the edge of a bimetallic weld), magnetic writing, etc.
False	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - False indications are not the result of magnetic forces. Examples are particles held mechanically or by gravity in shallow depressions or particles held by rust or scale on the surface.

Conclusion

In a practice of the project in AL-Heswa Thermal Power Station And Desalination Complex– Aden and Sanaa International Airport – Sanaa, there are some difficulties which confronted or encountered the project:

1. AL-Heswa Thermal Power Station And Desalination Complex– Aden
2. Sanaa International Airport – Sanaa

1. AL-Heswa Thermal Power Station And Desalination Complex– Aden

- A. There is not specialized section for Nondestructive Testing (NDT), but Nondestructive Testing (NDT) is combined with material test section.
- B. The operators have not sufficient experience and qualification to utilize the devices and dealing with it in Nondestructive Testing (NDT).
- C. Some instruments are not used, because the operators depends upon simple theories to performance the works.

2. Sanaa International Airport – Sanaa

- A. Procedures of applying the tests are confined or restricted due to the mother company, so that is carry out to difficulty or complicated the identify the theoretical part and practical part.
- B. Short time in the practice in NDT section, because a lot of time are spend to get the declaration or license of entrance.
- C. Some devices which utilized have a lot of functions, but utilized for one or two jobs, such as: bench unit of Magnetic Particles Inspection (MPI).

Piece Of Advice

If there are any students wants to enforcements the NDT project, preferable to them apply the theoretical part (formulae) and practical part (experiments), then compare them and notice the results.

Appendix I

Longitudinal Wave Velocity	Shear Wave Velocity	Wavelength
$V_L = \sqrt{\frac{E(1-\mu)}{\rho(1+\mu)(1-2\mu)}}$ <p>Where: V_L = Longitudinal Wave Velocity E = Modulus of Elasticity ρ = Density μ = Poisson's Ratio</p>	$V_S = \sqrt{\frac{E}{2\rho(1+\mu)}} \text{ or } \sqrt{\frac{G}{\rho}}$ <p>Where: V_S = Shear Wave Velocity E = Modulus of Elasticity ρ = Density μ = Poisson's Ratio G = Shear Modulus</p>	$\lambda = \frac{V}{f}$ <p>Where: λ = Wavelength V = Velocity f = Frequency</p>
Refraction (Snell's Law)	Acoustic Impedance	Reflection And Transmission Coefficients
$\frac{\sin \theta_i}{\sin \theta_r} = \frac{V_1}{V_2}$ <p>Where: θ_i = Angle of Incident Wave θ_r = Angle of Reflected Wave V_1 = Velocity of Incident Wave V_2 = Velocity of Reflected Wave</p>	$Z = \rho \times V$ <p>Where: Z = Acoustic Impedance ρ = Density V = Velocity</p>	$R = \frac{(Z_2 - Z_1)^2}{(Z_2 + Z_1)^2}$ <p>And $T = 1 - R$</p> <p>Where: R = Reflection Coefficient T = Transmission Coefficients Z_1 = Acoustic Impedance of Medium 1 Z_2 = Acoustic Impedance of Medium 2</p>